

Reliability and Maintainability – Key To Launch Vehicle Affordability

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SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

R&M is extremely critical to build safe, reliable, and cost effective systems. The challenges of today's unmanned and manned space flight programs demand the most efficient use of our technical knowledge base to develop cost effective and affordable systems. An efficient reliability and maintainability program is essential to meet the challenges for the nation's Space Program. This paper discusses the role of Reliability and Maintainability (R&M) and its potential impact on operational availability, and affordability. This includes discussion of the R&M elements that need to be addressed and the R&M analyses that need to be performed in order to support an affordable system design. The paper also provides some lessons learned on the impact of R&M on safety and affordability. Lessons learned discussed in this paper clearly demonstrate the importance of reliability and maintainability engineering in designing and operating safe and affordable launch systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

The United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and its commercial partners are in the midst of an effort to design and build a safe and more affordable shuttle replacement and a heavy lift vehicle to go to the moon and beyond. To achieve that, NASA is seeking more innovative and efficient approaches to reduce cost while maintaining a high level of safety and mission success. One area that has the potential to contribute to achieving NASA goals in safety and affordability is R&M engineering. Department of Defense (DOD) and industry experience have shown that optimized and adequate levels of R&M are critical for achieving high level of safety and mission success and low sustainment cost. Systems that are designed to be more reliable (fewer failures) and maintainable (fewer resources needed) can lower the total life cycle cost.

Lessons learned from the Space Shuttle Program (SSP) clearly demonstrate the impact of R&M engineering on life cycle cost. The Challenger and Columbia accidents are examples of the high cost of failure. Beside these major accidents, the SSP had to deal with very costly events such as pad aborts, scrubs, and technically related launch delays. These events had major impact on Shuttle sustainment cost. These accidents and other R&M events demonstrated that

insufficient Reliability, Maintainability, and Supportability (RMS) engineering analyses upfront in the design phase could severely increase the sustainment and program total life cycle cost. Dr. Griffin, a former NASA administrator, testified to a Congressional committee: "While the Shuttles capabilities are extensive and varied, it has proven to be extremely expensive to use, unreliable in its logistics, and operational fragile."

2 THE PARADIGM CHANGE

In the early days, the focus of space vehicle designers was mainly on system performance. Lessons learned from historical failure data of launch vehicles has shown that there is a need for creating the proper balance between performance, reliability, maintainability, safety, and cost. These lessons learned have forced a paradigm shift on how to design and build new launch vehicles [1].

In the recent years, NASA's R&M emphasis has shifted from a position of rigid requirements to a focus on customer needs. Historically, this process was relatively easy as applied to development of NASA flight and ground systems because R&M program requirements were largely predetermined based on the criticality classification of the mission. Instead of criticality, total mission cost and life cycle cost has become a more significant factor. As a result, program resources have become more constrained. In this new environment, the customer expects a supplier to manage risk and cost by selecting and implementing only those R&M program elements that offer a high return. Those suppliers which are most effective in managing and satisfying customer expectations will be assigned future responsibilities and recognized for their contribution to the NASA community [2]. In summary, early consideration of reliability, maintainability, and availability allows the greatest opportunity to affect initial and long-term costs to return maximum benefits. The level of reliability and maintainability designed into a product is instrumental to its success and helps achieve an affordable and sustainable design in today's resource limited environment.

3 BUILDING THE RELIABILITY AND MAINTAINABILITY CASES

Ensuring that new designs meet reliability and maintainability targets requires careful selection of equipment, materials and design architecture combined with progressive

estimation and verification of the predicted performance during the design phase.

Building the reliability and maintainability cases upfront in the design phase provides a structured method for identifying R&M risks, the practical measures needed to eliminate or mitigate them, and the tangible evidence required to demonstrate that mitigations have been implemented. The following sections discuss the organizational interfaces, analyses, and products of Reliability and Maintainability cases.

3.1 The Reliability Case

In building the reliability case, it is important to keep in mind that reliability engineering has major interfaces with safety, quality, maintainability, supportability, cost, test, and design engineering as shown in Fig. 1. As a result, a comprehensive reliability case taking into consideration the interfaces shown in Fig. 1 is critical for addressing the entire spectrum of engineering and programmatic concerns, from Loss of Mission (LOM) risk and the Loss of Crew (LOC) risk to sustainment and system life cycle costs.

Figure 1 - Reliability Major Interfaces

The principle aim of the reliability case is to generate the argument and the supporting evidence to insure that the product will meet the reliability requirements and achieve mission success. Fig. 2 shows examples of the techniques used to build an argument for a reliability case. The choice of techniques is primarily dependent upon the quality and quantity of information available and is tailored to fit the project or program under consideration. These reliability engineering analysis and design techniques are used throughout the design process and performed jointly with the various design-engineering teams to be effective and achieve the performance and reliability goals set by the program.

3.2 The Maintainability Case

Benjamin S. Blanchard [3] defines maintainability as, “an

inherent characteristic of system or product design, pertaining to the ease, accuracy, safety, and economy in the performance of maintenance actions; a design parameter related to the ability to maintain”

Figure 2 - The Reliability Case

In his book, he discusses the importance of incorporating maintainability upfront in the design process. Design for maintainability contributes to improved reliability, increased availability, improved performance, control of maintenance costs, improved capability and use of human resources, and increases safety. In other words, implementation of maintainability features in a design can bring about operational cost savings for both manned and unmanned systems. The programmatic benefits of designing system hardware and software for ease and reduction of maintenance are numerous as has been demonstrated in the NASA’s Hubble Space Telescope (HST) program. Maintenance in a hostile, microgravity environment is a difficult and undesirable task for humans. Minimal exposure time to this environment can be achieved by implementing maintainability features in the design. The most successful NASA programs have been those that included maintainability features in all facets of the life cycle [3].

As in building the reliability case, it is important to mention that maintainability engineering has major interfaces with other organizations as shown in Fig. 3. As a result, a comprehensive maintainability case, taking into consideration the interfaces shown in Fig. 3, is required in order to improve operational availability, optimize the logistic support infrastructure, reduce lifecycle cost, and provide data essential for project management.

The principle aim of the maintainability case is to generate the argument and the supporting evidence to insure that the product will meet the maintainability requirements and achieve mission success. Fig. 5 shows the different analysis and techniques that comprise a maintainability case. As in the reliability case, the maintainability analyses and techniques are tailored to fit the program or project goals and

objectives. These maintainability engineering analysis and design techniques are used throughout the design process and performed jointly with the various design-engineering teams to be effective and achieve the maintainability goals set by the program.

Figure 3 - Maintainability Major Interface

Figure 4 - The Maintainability Case

4 THE LINK OF R&M TO AFFORDABILITY

A task force chartered by the Department of Defense (DoD) in 1995 has defined Affordability as "a process for program management that will lead to affordable technology rather than a program for cost reduction."

The interest in affordability is understandable, given the consistent pressure to reduce the budget and the commercial industry involvement in space flight provide a compelling incentive to design for affordability.

In System design, the assumption is that the total life cycle cost will be justified according to how well the system performs its intended function over time. This assumption cannot be justified when a system fails to perform upon

demand or fails to perform repeatedly. It has been well documented that the effort spent during the concept and early design stages of a system development cycle could affect over 80% of the total system costs. For purposes of cost-effective and timely system development, Reliability, Maintainability, and Availability (RMA) engineering is virtually non-effective if implemented at the completion of the design phase. The earlier a potential event is addressed, the more prepared the engineering team can be to correct or alleviate potential problems.

Fig. 5 shows the strong relationship between R&M and supportability engineering and their resulting effect on system safety, and cost. Each of these engineering disciplines is inherently dependent on the analysis and products of the other to form an engineering process that ultimately results in a system that achieves the desired level of safety and affordability. A major space program cannot achieve high or ambitious levels of safety and affordability without strong commitment to a "Design for R&M" environment. History has shown us that good R&M engineering can pay off in terms of mission success and affordability.

Supportability and Maintainability costs include the cost of operations and of maintaining the system. Obviously, maintainability costs are a direct function of reliability, incurring the costs of corrective and preventive maintenance that increase the supportability cost of the system. Although most systems are designed for a specified life, the reality is many operate far longer than their original design life. The ability to consider lifetime extensions and the cost-effectiveness of the extensions is directly correlated to the reliability, maintainability, and supportability of the system. The HST is a good example of how extensive R&M efforts can pay off in terms of extended service life, mission success, and cost efficient operation.

One way to increase affordability is simply by avoiding the cost of failure, and designing for reliability through robustness. A robust design is one that is tolerant to variations in its operational environment and works acceptably well under the entire range of environments that it may encounter. Robust Design focuses on improving the fundamental function of the product or process by developing flexible designs, concurrent engineering, and designing products and processes that are minimally impacted by external forces such as environment, customer use, or manufacturing conditions.

The affordability development effort is a continuous process, starting at the earliest program phase and proceeding through the subsequent phases of development, production, operation and support and disposal/replacement. RMA requirements must be specified and concepts implemented to ensure system performance goals and costs are properly balanced.

Systems with low reliability and high down time resulting from poor maintainability will demonstrate low levels of availability, higher support cost and higher life cycle cost due to the increased number and length of repair cycles. Systems with high reliability and lower downtime will demonstrate high availability, lower operating cost and lower Life Cycle

Cost (LCC).

Reliability and maintainability analyses provide essential data required to perform LCC. Failure rates and restoration times are essential in projecting the logistics costs associated with a program/project. These analysis impact redundancy decisions, the number of spares required, the labor-hours required to restore items to operation, impact on crew workloads, etc. R&M estimations and data are essential for a successful LCC effort. Early R&M involvement with the identification of the program metrics to be applied as well as the LCC effort will enhance the capability to consider cost in decisions concerning implementation or technology application and reduce overall LCC.

Figure 5 - R&M Relationship to Safety and Affordability

5 NASA LESSONS LEARNED

This section provides lessons learned from the Space Shuttle Program (SSP) and the HST. The SSP cases address the design and process reliability problems that led to the Columbia and Challenger accidents, while the HST case demonstrates how extensive R&M efforts can pay off in terms of extended service life, mission success, and cost efficient operation.

5.1 The Space Shuttle Cases

The SSP was a very successful program in terms of safety and mission success. Unfortunately, two major accidents occurred in the life of the program that had major impact on affordability and sustainment cost. They were the Challenger and the Columbia Accidents.

For the Challenger accident case, Fig. 6 below shows the field joint design flow on the Challenger and previous Shuttle flights. According to a published report about the Challenger accident, the causes and contributing factors are summarized below:

- The zinc chromate putty frequently failed and permitted the gas to erode the primary O-rings.

- The particular material used in the manufacture of the shuttle O-rings was the wrong material to use at low temperatures.
- Elastomers become brittle at low temperatures.

Figure 6 - Solid Rocket Motor Field Joint

For the Columbia case, Fig. 7 below shows the area of the External Tank (ET) foam loss that contributed to the Columbia accident. According to published report about the Columbia accident, the causes and contributing factors are summarized as follows:

- A breach in the Thermal Protection System (TPS), caused by the left bipod ramp foam insulation from the ET striking the left wing leading edge.
- There were large gaps in NASA's knowledge about the foam [4].
- Cryopumping and cryoingestion were experienced during tanking, launch, and ascent.
- Dissections of foam revealed subsurface flaws and defects as contributing to the loss of foam [5].

Figure 7 - Bipod ramp foam loss

The Challenger and Columbia accidents were very expensive in terms of dollars and human lives. They are clear examples of the severe impact of unreliability on safety, affordability, and sustainment cost.

5.2 The Hubble Space Telescope Case

As mentioned earlier, the HST, shown in Fig. 8, is a good example of how extensive R&M efforts can pay off in terms of extended service life, mission success, and cost efficient operation. The HST was designed for maintainability and serviceability. Launched in 1990, it is still functioning today. It is a good demonstration of successful implementation of maintainability principles that can reduce risk by increasing operational availability and reducing lifecycle costs. This includes:

- Enhanced System Readiness/Availability
- Reduced Downtime
- Supportable Systems
- Ease of Troubleshooting and Repair
- System Growth Opportunities
- Hardware/Software Modifications
- Interchangeability
- Modular Designs
- Decreased Storage Considerations
- Reduced Maintenance Manpower
- Reduced Operational Costs
- Compatibility with other Programs
- Reduced Management Overhead

It is important to mention that the “design for maintainability” process performed on the HST program allowed a major problem, the mirror defect, to be resolved. This demonstrates that “design for maintainability” can have unforeseen, mission saving benefits.

Figure 8 - The Hubble Space Telescope

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

R&M is extremely critical to build safe, reliable, and cost effective systems. The challenges of today’s unmanned and manned space flight programs demand the most efficient use of our technical knowledge base to develop cost effective and affordable systems. An efficient reliability and maintainability program is essential to meet the challenges for the nation’s Space Program. Lessons learned from the NASA programs clearly demonstrate the importance of reliability and maintainability engineering in designing and operating safe and affordable launch systems.

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